

Compton Iteration

Adolf Cusmariu

adolcus@gmail.com

In the **Compton Effect** [1], a photon with initial wavelength λ_0 bouncing at angle θ_1 off a stationary electron undergoes unexpectedly a wavelength increase:

$$\lambda_1 = \lambda_0 + \lambda_c(1 - \cos\theta_1)$$

where

$$\lambda_0 = \text{X-ray wavelength} = 70.9 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}$$

$$\lambda_c = \text{Compton wavelength} = 2.426 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}$$

θ_1 = Photon bounce angle

the impact also ejecting the electron at angle ϕ ; see graphic below (photon in red, electron in blue).

Under suitable conditions, a collision of the resulting photon with an available electron would produce a further increase in wavelength:

$$\lambda_2 = \lambda_1 + \lambda_c(1 - \cos\theta_2) = \lambda_0 + \lambda_c(2 - \cos\theta_1 - \cos\theta_2)$$

so in principle, multiple collisions would yield successively longer wavelengths (and shorter frequencies):

$$\lambda_n = \lambda_0 + \lambda_c(n - \sum_k \cos\theta_k)$$

a case of 'Compton Iteration'. Of course, the challenge is 'directing' the photon to impact repeatedly, yielding eventually a controlled frequency down-shift. To this end, an elliptical chamber with a mirrored interior would control the bounces because of the 'return to focus' property of the ellipse; thus placing electron candidates at each focus would trap the photon and force it to continue its 'Compton Iteration'; see a graphic below, showing three caroms.

Some practical considerations arise immediately:

- 1) Dimensions of the chamber: Semi-major & Semi-minor axes
- 2) Entry point for a photon into the chamber
- 3) Electron insertions at each Focus
- 4) Orientation controls on carom surfaces
- 5) Sensor positioning within the chamber to measure carom angles
- 6) A carom counter to check iteration progress
- 7) Absorption of ejected electrons after each carom to eliminate interfering collisions
- 8) Exit point of a photon once the desired wavelength has been reached

Let's examine some simple cases.

Assume all bounce angles θ_k are at $45^\circ = \pi/4$. Wavelength at the n -th iteration is clearly

$$\lambda_n = \lambda_0 + n\lambda_c(1 - \cos(\pi/4))$$

How many iterations are needed to effectively double the initial wavelength λ_0 ? That is, for what n is

$$2\lambda_0 = \lambda_0 + n\lambda_c(1 - \cos(\pi/4)) ?$$

Easily then

$$n = \text{round}\{\lambda_0/(\lambda_c(1 - \cos(\pi/4)))\} = 100$$

Given the enormity of the speed-of-light $c = 3 \times 10^8 \text{m/s}$, assuming a modest-sized enclosure so all photon bounce-paths L are (say) $L = 1\text{m}$, wavelength doubling would take about (using $n = 100$)

$$T = nL/c = (1/3)\mu\text{sec}$$

Conversely, in **1 hour** ($T = 3,600\text{sec}$) and $L = 1$, there would be $N = Tc = 3,600 \times 3 \times 10^8$ iterations, resulting in a wavelength

$$\lambda_N = \lambda_0 + N\lambda_c(1 - \cos(\pi/4)) = 0.7674\text{m}$$

an enormous increase from the original $\lambda_0 = 70.9 \times 10^{-12}\text{m}$ through Compton Iteration; the resulting frequency would be merely

$$\omega_N = c/\lambda_N = 391 \text{ MHz}$$

As a laboratory experiment to study collision control through Compton Iteration, it seems possible that a photon's frequency - hence its energy - could be reduced dramatically by running this iteration at will, perhaps to the point of near-exhaustion.

Reference

[1] A. H. Compton, 'A quantum theory of the scattering of x-rays by light elements', The Physical Review, Vol. 21, No.5, May, 1923.